

REQUIREMENTS FOR SPEECH DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: The article describes the formation of two interrelated areas of speech education in preschool age: teaching the native language (phonetics, vocabulary, grammar) and linguistic cognitive activity and methods of communication.

Key words: Preschool age, environment, game, education, language, speech, development, personality, activity.

Teaching the native language in preschool educational institutions is carried out in various types of children's activities: artistic, in activities related to familiarization with environmental phenomena, in all other types of activities, as well as outside of them - in games and cocktail events. , increases in everyday life. However, in this case, the main training is considered to be teaching the native language and speech development, in which the teacher must solve the following tasks:

- supporting children's interest in the personalities and activities of their peers, helping them establish dialogical communication in joint games and activities. Various means of communication - verbal, gestural, pantomime methods are used differentially, taking into account the specific situation;

- phonemic perception of speech, development of pronunciation and tonal aspects of speech. Learn to identify and correctly pronounce sounds that are articulatory and acoustically close to each other (hard and soft, muffled and sonorous, whistling and hissing, sonorous sounds). Practicing the correct

pronunciation of sounds in words and short statements, short poems. Training in voluntary control of tone, tempo and pitch of pronunciation.

- improving the perception of the meaning of words, enriching children's speech with antonyms, synonyms, ambiguous words, generalizing nouns, activation of figurative words, comparisons, interjections (epithets), specific verbs;

- help to master complex cases of changing words (main agreement and indicative agreement, plural nouns, undifferentiated nouns, imperative mood and forms of verbs, formation of improved and imperfect forms of verbs). Improving the structure of sentences, promoting the active use of various sentence structures in speech - simple, complex sentences and the speech of strangers. In the process of mastering grammatical means, maintain a critical attitude towards speech, strive to speak correctly;

- support children's interest in telling stories on their own initiative or at the suggestion of adults, teach them to tell stories, pictures, impressions of personal experience in words in the form of a short statement, story, reflection, description;

- in the sudden creation of words, in playing with sounds and rhymes, in conducting tests with a word in a unique way to the sound of a word, their sound and meaning, assumptions, the meaning of words maintain interest in interpretation. To develop an understanding of the linguistic environment in the simplest way, to introduce children to the concepts of "sound", "word", "speech".

Language acquisition occurs in the case of expanding knowledge about the phenomena of the surrounding world and various relationships. However, the formation of the task of understanding language and speech at the level of the child's abilities is a central link in the development of the language of a preschool child. In the field of language use, three links are distinguished: establishing emotional connections with others; be able to express an opinion, create informational text; able to establish verbal cooperation with a partner. In older

preschool age, communication with peers comes to the fore as an area of communicative hobby, in which the child satisfies his need for communication, realizes his achievements in the growth and development of linguistic knowledge and fluency, and learns to cooperate. with a partner.

In order to create the necessary conditions for the development of children's speech, the teacher should follow the main directions of work in this regard:

1. Development of fluent speech

Regarding preschool children, it is necessary to consider two forms of speech - dialogical and monologue. Dialogue is characterized by an exchange of views between two or more speakers on a topic related to a situation. In the dialogue, all types of syntactically simple expressions, exclamatory (please, request), interrogative sentences are shown using prepositions. Linguistic means are supported by gestures and facial expressions.

The teacher must create a situation in which children can create a dialogue using various language means - asking, answering, explaining, begging, biting, etc. let him face the need. To do this, it is necessary to use a conversation on various topics related to the child's life in the family, in a preschool educational institution, his relationships with friends and adults, his interests and impressions. It is in dialogue that the ability to listen to the interlocutor, ask questions and answer according to the content is developed. These qualities and skills are also necessary for the education and development of monologue speech. Collaborative activities are important for dialogical communication with peers. This activity is formed gradually. First, children interpret what is happening and act alongside. In this situation, speech is stimulated by the presence of a peer and the opportunity to talk with him, performs the function of planning and organizing his activities, as well as establishing social communication. Communication between children is predominantly practical.

The dialogue is often conducted in such a way that the child reacts to the partner's short bites with actions or expresses his attitude to the event through non-verbal means. There are many folk games with the help of which children learn to pay attention to each other, recognize friends by voice, notice details of their appearance, and communicate verbally.

To establish a dialogue, it is recommended to use board and printed games ("lotto", "dominoes"). Playing in pairs, children master the techniques of dialogic cooperation: taking turns, politely addressing each other, arguing their point of view, coordinating their thoughts with their partner. As a basis for knowledge, such games can involve various types of speech tasks, for example: choosing words with a given sound, classifying acoustically and articulatory sounds that are close to each other, classifying generic names, collaboratively telling a story based on a series of photographs, etc.

2. Development of monologue speech.

When teaching children to form a detailed thought, the teacher needs to develop in them the simplest knowledge about the structure of the text (beginning, middle, end), an understanding of the connections between a sentence and the components of a thought. . It is this indicator (a means of communication between sentences) that is one of the important conditions for the formation of fluency of speech thought. In any complete sentence there will be common variants of combining phrases. The most common way to connect sentences is a chain.

Pronouns, lexical repetition and synonymous substitution are the main tools of this communication. Chain communication makes speech more flexible and colorful, since when mastering this method the child avoids repeating the same word. The teacher must teach children to connect sentences in parallel, while the sentences are not connected to each other, but compared or even contrasted (A strong wind was blowing. The rabbit hid in the nest). When teaching older preschoolers how to compose texts fluently, special attention must

be paid to developing the ability to reveal the topic and main idea of the spoken word, and to put a title to the text.

Conclusion: When developing the sound side of speech, the teacher must teach the child to take into account the compatibility of thoughts with the goals and conditions of communication based on the subject, topic of the statement and audience. In the process of work, the teacher must be able to listen and determine the sound structure of a word, the place of stress in a word, develop a sense of rhyme and weight, give accurate pronunciation, different intonation characteristics of words, phrases, sentences, it is necessary to use exercises that help form. The teacher develops children's thinking and all aspects of their speech, including figurative, to the extent that this allows them to get acquainted with the surrounding life, family and preschool educational institution, people's work, social events and phenomena, wildlife and the objective world. . Preschoolers actively perceive existence and engage with life in the environment, which leads to a rapid increase in their vocabulary.

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